

A Note on an Attempt to prepare *p*-Diphenylene.

BY ANUKUL CHANDRA SIRCAR AND JNANENDRA NARAYAN MAJUMDAR.

This note gives a further (compare Sircar and De, this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 245) account of the works that have been done with the object of preparing *p*-diphenylene, which according to Kaufler's theory (*Annalen*, 1907, 361, 151) must be the hypothetical parent hydrocarbon of which diphenyl and its substitution products are the derivatives.

As before (Sircar and De, *loc. cit.*) *p*: *p*'-di-iodo-diphenyl and finely divided copper powder (Natur Kupfer C) were used, and as the result of a large number of experiments carried out under varied conditions, it has now been found that if the reaction is carried out in a perfectly dry sealed tube at a temperature of 300-310°, a substance melting at 304-305° is obtained. From a determination of its molecular weight and study of other properties it appears to be tetraphenylene,

a hitherto unknown hydrocarbon. If the reaction is performed in a sealed tube, containing a small quantity of water, at 280-300°, the copper replaces the iodine atoms by hydrogen and diphenyl is formed.

It thus appears that, though *p*-diphenylene could not be prepared, as a result of the present investigation, (a) a new hydrocarbon has probably been obtained, and (b) under definite conditions, finely powdered copper can replace iodine atoms in an organic molecule by hydrogen.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Tetraphenylene.—An intimate mixture of *p*: *p*'-di-iodo-diphenyl (5 g.) and finely divided copper powder (10 g.) was heated in a dry sealed tube at 300-310° for 15 hours. The copper lost its lustre. The reaction product was extracted with boiling benzene from which, on concentration, the hydrocarbon separated as minute white plates, m. p. 304-305°.

It is insoluble in the cold in all the common organic solvents, but dissolves in hot nitrobenzene or pyridine and with difficulty in benzene. (Found: C, 94.89; H, 5.84. $C_{14}H_{10}$ requires C, 94.73; H, 5.26 per cent.). 0.3219 G. of the substance dissolved in 24.48 g. of pyridine gave elevation of boiling point 0.11° and 0.13° .

Found: M. W. =

(i) 350, 296 (Warner's method).

(ii) 343, 290 (Rose Innes' method).

(iii) 315, 266 (Walden's method).

$C_{14}H_{10}$ requires M. W. = 304.

Diphenyl.—An intimate mixture of 5 g. of *p*:*p'*-di-iodo-diphenyl with double the amount of copper powder and 1 c. c. of water was heated in a sealed tube at $280-300^{\circ}$ for 5 to 6 hours, after which time the copper was found to have lost its lustre. The contents of the tube were extracted with ether, the ether distilled off, and the residue crystallised from alcohol in minute white plates (m. p. 70°). By determinations of the percentage composition, molecular weight and mixed melting point, and also by its conversion into *p*:*p'*-dibromo-diphenyl (prisms, m. p. 164°), the substance was identified to be diphenyl.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY, DACCA.

Received April 25, 1928.